

Shifting Policies, Static Science? Examining the disconnect between Science Technology and Innovation Policies and Research Fronts in Colombia

ABSTRACT

Newly elected governments may introduce new Science, Technology, and Innovation Policies (STIP) to the policy-making agenda. However, identifying shifts in STIP priorities following governmental transitions remains a methodological and empirical challenge. This study examines whether the STIP priorities introduced by different government administrations in Colombia align with the country's national research fronts. Two datasets were employed: a manually curated database of 443 funding calls issued between 2007 and 2022, and a collection of over 42,000 research articles indexed in Scopus from 1996 to 2022. The findings indicate that STIP priorities are largely disconnected from national research fronts. While the number of research fields supported by STIP has increased over time, national research fronts have remained relatively static and have not demonstrated significant diversification. A limited number of research fields—those characterized by high betweenness centrality—exhibited moderate correlation across both STIP priorities and research fronts. These fields include public health; environmental and occupational health; general medicine; infectious diseases; agricultural and biological sciences; agronomy and crop science; drug discovery; general and renewable energy; fuel technology; economics and econometrics; and sociology and political science. The implications of these findings are discussed in relation to path dependency in national research agendas.

1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Electoral democracies vote for government candidates each four to six years (Statista 2020). If not re-elected, each government transition might bring a new political ideology and vision for the country's policies, including STIP (Science, Technology and Innovation Policy/es). In an ideal scenario, a country would have a long-run vision for STIP despite the government administration in office — however, those cases are exceptional (Ito et al. 2017; Stage & Aagaard 2020; Weber et al. 2009). Accordingly, for most electoral democracies, each government in office will bring its STIP priorities to the policy-making table. Therefore, how to identify the changing STIP priorities when a new government takes office? Are those priorities in line with current national capabilities to produce knowledge? Is there a misalignment between STIP and the available national knowledge base? Also, are strategic fields maintaining their key position in the knowledge-based structure despite STIP transitions? While there is well-grounded literature on STIP, there is an underdeveloped stream of studies focusing on middle-low-income countries using techniques from scientometrics. Consequently, this study aims to correlate research fields prioritized by STIP deployed by different government administrations and national research fronts in Colombia.

STIP can be defined as a set of processes that affect how the rules and practices to develop basic or applied research are designed and implemented within national borders for private and public actors (Edler et al. 2012; Meyer-Krahmer 1984; Neal et al. 2008). Such a process also expects to shape and give direction to knowledge production (Boswell & Smith 2017; Li et al. 2022; Louder et al. 2021; Shibayama & Baba 2015). Since *Science, The Endless Frontier* (1945) —an influential STIP precursor—, STIP literature has made diverse and multiple contributions, particularly on theoretical/conceptual frameworks for improving science/technology evaluation and their impact (Arnold 2004; Boswell & Smith 2017; Edler et al. 2012; Gök & Edler 2012; Hicks & Isett 2020; Jordan 2010; Kuhlmann 2003; Louder et al. 2021; Magro & Wilson 2013, 2019; Nielsen 2003; Pahl et al. 2008; Pohoryles 2006; Russo & Rossi 2009); and STIP impact on (actors of) national science and technology systems performance (Ahrweiler et al. 2015; Avellar & Botelho 2018; Block & Krull 1990; Bodmer 1994; Bozeman & Link 2015; Confraria et al. 2017; Crouch et al. 1986; Davis 1989; Fortin & Currie 2013; De Gorter & Swinnen 1998; Guskov et al. 2016; Himanen et al. 2009; Inglesi-Lotz & Pouris 2011; Isaksen et al. 2017; Ito et al. 2017; Jasinski 2003; Mansfield 1991, 1998; Meyer-Krahmer 1984; Nikzad 2019; Pianta & Sirilli 1997; Samara et al. 2012; Shibayama & Baba 2015; Svarc et al. 2011; N. Wang et al. 2016; Weber et al. 2009; Zhang et al. 2011). Yet, despite such a dutiful research program, studying STIP via scientometrics techniques in middle-low-income countries is still an emerging agenda.

Studies on STIP using scientometrics techniques have been overly focused on (researchers/journals from) higher-income countries. For example, a collection of studies estimated the relationship between funding and citation impact at the country (e.g., Japan or Spain) (Rodríguez-Navarro & Brito 2022; Shibayama & Baba 2015) or regional levels (e.g., Europe (Gök et al. 2016)). There is also a specific interest in the relationship between funding research and impact at the journal level (e.g., *Cell* and *Physical Review Letters*) (J Rigby 2011). Few of the published studies on middle-low income countries provide evidence of changes in the impact of a novel research evaluation system in South Africa (Inglesi-Lotz & Pouris 2011), the remarkable awakening of China as a global scientific powerhouse and the successful national STIP features and the growing citation of national STIP in research articles (Ito et al. 2017; Li et al. 2022), the STIP effects of Russia's *restoration* after 2006 (Guskov et al. 2016), and the incentive-STIP impact on Brazil innovation activities (Avellar & Botelho 2018).

This study focuses on Colombia, a country that sparks interest since it is one of the most research-productive countries in Latin America and the Caribbean despite immense restrictions on

research and development investment and research-oriented human capital (Cortés & Andrade 2022a, 2022b; Cortés & Ramírez-Cajiao 2023a). The R&D expenditure as a percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) have never surpassed the 1% and the number of researchers in R&D per million people have never surpassed 100 when the world average in 2018 was 1597 (The World Bank 2022). Concerning Colombia's STIP context, its science system was established throughout the 1990s decade at the same time that the governments opened the economy to the international markets (Fundación Alejandro Ángel Escobar 2007; UNESCO 2010; Vasen et al. 2023). Ever since, five STIP from 1991 to 2021 have been released with no clear issuing frequency or revision (DNP 2021). Two policies were emitted in the 1990s with a two-year difference. Two policies during 2000-2009 and one in 2021. The term 'innovation' was added until the last two (2009, 2021). Also, five policies over 30 years are no clear reflection of governments aimed to last four years in office—with the exceptions of 2006-2010 and 2015-2018 when the presidential election was permitted in Colombia. Analyzing five STIP will not provide granular evidence of the sort required. In consequence, we turn our focus on the public research funding calls issued by the national government and the Ministry of STI (formerly: Colciencias).

These public research funding calls are the product of a planning exercise by multiple ministries (e.g., Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and Ministry of Information and Communication Technologies) and the Department of National Planning. The public funding calls purpose is to allocate the investment in STI based on strategic challenges to materialize the major commitments of the national government to mobilize the knowledge society (MinCiencias 2022a). That entails the knowledge production (e.g., production of research outputs). The public research funding calls in multiple ways are the concerted effort to mediate the long-term national STIP direction and government strategic priorities, and the institutional (e.g., Universities) and individual (e.g., researchers) efforts to respond to those challenges as scientific activities and outputs (McNie et al. 2016; John Rigby 2011; Torregrosa-Hetland et al. 2019). In sum, assembling public funding research calls as a mediation instruments to deploy and fund government priorities in STIP to certain fields and disciplines, is an output of the coordination of multiple government agencies and ministries which intention is create public value and attend societal problems. Thereby, the orientation of STIP is problem-driven with a defined intention of supporting fields/disciplines of interest to contribute to the understanding and solution of those diagnosed problems.

The contribution of this study builds on the research agenda on STIP and scientometrics and the scarcity—although necessary—of in-depth individual national studies in the contexts of middle-low income countries (Cortés et al. 2021; Gonzalez-Brambila et al. 2016; Katz 2000; Vasen et al. 2023). Furthermore, it sheds light on methodological and analytical appraisals to study the (mis)alignment between STIP and national research fronts via well-established methodologies from scientometrics (Callon et al. 1983, 1991; Kessler 1963). We use two inputs to correlate research fields prioritized by STIP deployed by different government administrations and national research fronts. First, to analyze government STIP transitions, we reproduced the findings of co-word network analysis applied to a hand-curated dataset of 443 research funding calls from three government administrations in Colombia from 2007 to 2022 (Cortés & Ramírez-Cajiao 2023a, 2023b). Second, to examine national research fronts, we conducted a bibliographic coupling analysis on a sub-sample of 42,000+ research articles authored by at least one author affiliated with a Colombian institution indexed in Scopus from 1996 to 2022 (Scopus 2022). After this introduction, the methodology section presents the datasets and methods used, followed by the results, and then the discussion and concluding remarks sections.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data

2.1.1 Bibliographic data

We sourced the bibliographic data from Elsevier's Scopus (2022). Scopus is one of the two canonical bibliographic databases along with the Web of Science (Waltman & Larivière 2020). Compared to the latter, Scopus has broader coverage in the net number of journals, humanities & social science-related disciplines, and middle-low income authors participation (Singh et al. 2021; Thelwall & Sud 2022). We focused the period of our analysis from 1996 to 2022 due to Scopus indexing precision limitations for large bibliometric analyses (Ioannidis et al. 2016).

The search query sourced research articles with at least one author affiliated with an institution located in Colombia. The search query was formulated as follows: *AFFILCOUNTRY (colombia) AND SRCTYPE (j) AND DOCTYPE (ar) AND PUBYEAR > 1995 AND PUBYEAR < 2023*. As a result, Scopus found 122,000+ documents that matched those criteria. Table 1 displays the bibliometric descriptives of the complete sample. For the last 5-years 2018-2022, the average of articles published was 11,810, particularly in medicine, followed by agricultural and biological sciences, engineering, social sciences, and physics and astronomy. The most productive institutions were public universities (e.g., Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Universidad de Antioquia, or Universidad del Valle), among a few were private (e.g., Universidad de Los Andes and Pontificia Universidad Javeriana). On the other hand, the most frequent serials in which Colombian research is being published were local journals on medicine (e.g., *Biomedica* or *Revista Colombiana De Cardiología*) and engineering (e.g., *Dyna Colombia*), except for the multidisciplinary mega journal *PLoS One*.

Among the purposes of this study is to determine national matured research fronts. Hence, we considered for the analysis only journals with at least 50 articles published by at least one author affiliated with a Colombian institution from 1996-2022, an average of ~2 articles per year. After removing potential duplicates, the sub-sample comprised 42,826 articles (35% of the complete sample). This sub-sampling might be biased against disciplines with lower productivity/maturity in the country, excluding them from the process of detecting research fronts. Scopus classified the national production of articles in 27 fields, the most relevant showed in Table 1. Among those with lower productivity and that might be omitted from the process of identifying research fronts are general veterinary (with 2700+ articles between 1996-2022), general nursing (2500+), and general neuroscience (2100+). For social sciences and humanities, there are 7400+ articles. However, with the subsample of matured research fronts, we reached a more refined analysis by comprising over 150 research fields out of 27 of the full sample. We considered all fields of the journals in which each pair of articles via bibliographic coupling was published and its frequency since a journal could be assigned to more than one research field. This approach is more flexible and inclusive for journals with multiple assigned disciplines. More on bibliographic coupling in section 2.2.1.

2.1.2 Funding calls data

We reproduced the data base and replicated the methodology implemented by Cortés and Ramírez-Cajiao to build up the content structure of public research funding calls via co-word analysis (Callon et al. 1983; Cortés & Ramírez-Cajiao 2023a, 2023b). This curated database of the content of public research funding calls was sourced from the national government and Ministry of STI (formerly: Colciencias) digital archive. The digital archive keeps information from 2005 onwards (Colciencias 2005; MinCiencias 2022b). There is no full availability of metadata of the summary, keywords, research fields priorities, among other contents of interests. Therefore, the authors hand-curated essential information by RC by looking at the complete terms of reference.

The search was focused on research-oriented public research calls, such as basic/applied research project funding, research evaluation funding, private R&D activities funding, international academic mobility, junior researcher, masters, and Ph.D. grants, and research institutes/centers strengthening. Tax incentives, national research group assessments, national scientific journal assessments, technical services outsourcing for the Ministry of STI, and research calls of the sort were excluded. For those public funding research calls with no information about the key research/scientific areas prioritized, the authors scanned the documents in search for fields to be supported or fostered by them (e.g., biotechnology, agricultural production, museology, information technology, and so forth). Figure 1 reports a section of the text to the terms of references of a public research call which priority are, translated into in English, *energy and natural resources, biotechnology, health, material science and electronics, information and telecommunication technologies, logistics and design, citizenship building and social inclusion*.

In those cases in which the prioritized research fields/disciplines were not standardized (e.g., mention to *sustainability* in a research call in 2007, mention to *sustainability science* in 2010, mention to *sustainability* in 2015, and so forth) a standardization of key terms were needed. The standardization method used was to match the hand-curated key terms with the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) (Scopus 2020). The ASJC is a system standardized by Scopus that assigns a serial title to one or more fields. There are 334 fields in five areas: physical sciences, life sciences, health sciences, social sciences and humanities, and multidisciplinary. In doing so, homonyms term we unified and merged into a single one. For instance, key terms such as *biotech, bio-inspired tech*, and the sort were unified under the ASJC field of *Biotechnology*.

Where key terms were unmatched with corresponding ASJC categories, the authors performed a search for the most cited article in the Scopus bibliographic database (Scopus 2020). The authors searcher for the article using the key terms on the article title, an accurate search request since it assures the key terms' centrality to the article's research topic (Nakamura et al. 2019). Following that, the entire set of ASJC fields associated with that journal were listed as the correspondent field for that key term. For instance, the key term *Cultural processes* had no similar match among ASJC fields; the highest cited article with that key term in the title was '*Demography and cultural evolution: How adaptive cultural processes can produce maladaptive losses- the Tasmanian case*', published in a journal which assigned fields ASJC were *Museology; History; Archeology*. The authors only considered calls with three or more ASJC to be processed to form at least a triad of concepts. The elected government term last four years.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 National research fronts

Multiple science mapping techniques unveil national research fronts (Börner et al. 2012; Huang et al. 2021; Shiffrin & Börner 2004). The technique implemented here to map the research fronts of Colombia is bibliographic coupling (Kessler 1963). This technique unveils the structure of the knowledge base and research fronts by connecting two documents if both cite a common reference (Kessler 1963). Bibliographic coupling outperforms, although moderately, other techniques to identify research fronts, such as co-citation or direct citation (Boyack & Klavans 2010). Moreover, it is quite versatile in processing inter/multi/transdisciplinary bibliographic data, from sustainable development to the whole set of publications of the journal *Nature* since its inception (Gates et al. 2019; Nakamura et al. 2019). The equation for obtaining a bibliographic coupling network is $B_{coup} = Ax A'$, where A is a document and x is a cited reference matrix (Aria & Cuccurullo 2017). The element b_{ij} indicates how many bibliographic couplings exist between documents i and j . B_{coup} is both a

non-negative/symmetrical matrix (Aria & Cuccurullo 2017). Fig. 2 displays the core process of this approach.

To reduce redundancy and improve clarity and segmentation between research fronts identified, we refined the bibliographic coupling at the research field level instead of the level using the ASJC standard. Since some journals are classified in more than one field, we unchained the ASJC code fields of each journal and built an edge list to model the network. Let us suppose that articles *A* and *B* belong to two different journals: article *A* to journal *X* and article *B* to journal *Y*. Let us also assume that both journals *X* and *Y* are classified in two fields each: *Field 1 of journal X* and *Field 2 of journal X*, and *Field 1 of journal Y* and *Field 2 of journal Y*—however it could be over two fields. Since we are interested in identifying research fronts as fields and not individual documents, the expanded bibliographic coupling network by field would be modeled as shown in Fig. 3. In contrast of count as one publication-one field, we will count the frequency of fields in the networks modeled. This adjustment goes in line with the discussion outlined previously on the plausible exclusion of research fields as research fronts because of the *maturity* threshold of excluding journals with less than 50 articles published between 1996-2020 by at least one (co)author from Colombia. Table 2 displays the full and normalized counts in a 0-10 scale by research fields. As previously stated, the research field count after the bibliographic coupling network modeling provides an inclusive and refined view of research fronts that the 27 fields reported by Scopus for the initial query.

2.2.2 *Funding calls research structure*

The co-word analysis enable us to build a structure (i.e., network) of collocated ASJC identified in each research call. For instance, if a research call was focused on funding research related to biotechnology, general biology, and general computer science, the three fields (i.e., nodes) are connected via the call in which they were decided to receive support from a specific government STIP. The co-word network equation is $B_{cn} = A' \times A$, where *A* is a *Call x ASJC field* matrix, where *ASJC field* is the standardized funding call key terms matched using ASJC; and B_{ij} indicates the number of co-occurrences between *ASJC field j* and *i* (Aria & Cuccurullo 2017). Fig. 4 presents the core process of this approach.

We will analyze the funding calls of three government administrations: 2007-2010, 2011-2014, and 2015-2018. The reasoning for choosing such periods corresponds to two conditions. First, in Colombia, each government administration last 4 years—the periods mentioned above (Constitución Política de Colombia 1991). Second, three to five-year windows are well-established standards for large-scale and institutional bibliometric assessments, which gives a four-year window a grounded and practical period for both government administration periods and scientific activity valuation (Bornmann et al. 2012; J. Wang 2013).

2.2.3 *STIP and research fronts correlation*

We correlate strategic fields defined by governments via their STIP—reflected by the funding calls they open—with the research fronts which emerge from the national research output. Here we consider two main factors: periods and indices to correlate.

First, as mentioned before, we will analyze the funding calls of three government administrations: 2007-2010, 2011-2014, and 2015-2018. The four-year period also is a well-established standard in bibliometric assessment. That is partly because scientific endeavor development and subsequent impact take time. Therefore, it is not accurate to correlate the structure of funding calls of the 2007-2010 government with 2007-2010 research fronts, which, supposedly,

have been influenced by the STIP direction/priority of such a government. Consequently, it is more methodologically sound to correlate the structure of funding calls of the 2007-2010 government with the research fronts of 2011-2014, the accumulation of the next 4-four-year period.

Second, the appropriate selection of a measure that can reflect the strategic relevance of a research field among both the content structure of funding calls and research fronts. For this, we consider betweenness centrality the most appropriate network analysis index (Freeman 1977; Shugars & Scarpino 2021). Betweenness centrality is a measure of the number of the shortest path that passes through a given node (i.e., research field). Such a property translates into the capacity of the research field to enable—or constrain—the information flow between clustered fields.

The equation for the betweenness calculation is $C_B(p_k) = \sum_{i < j}^n \frac{g_{ij}(p_k)}{g_{ij}}$; $i \neq j \neq k$, where g_{ij} is the shorter path that links nodes p_i and p_j and $g_{ij}(p_k)$ is the shorter path that links nodes p_i and p_j through node p_k (Opsahl et al. 2010). Since both funding calls and research fronts structures were analyzed via network analysis using the same AJSC standard for node identification (i.e., fields), we can compute and correlate the betweenness centrality index for any network produced in both contexts. The network layout used was hive plots (Engle & Whalen 2012; Krzywinski et al. 2012). It represents nodes uniformly across defined axes. Each axis was defined as a research area. Fig. 5 presents a summary of the methodology.

3 RESULTS

Fig. 6 presents a replication of the betweenness indices of research fields by area and period of the funding calls from Cortés and Ramirez-Cajiao study (2023a) as an overview of the changing priority of research fields according to each government STIP. Cortés and Ramirez-Cajiao (2023a) found a continuous increase in the density (i.e., how connected the nodes are over potential connections) of the co-word network composed by research fields of the funding calls from 2007 to 2022. The network density in 2007-2011 was not remarkably dense, with a 18% density, whereas for 2019-2022 it had a 97% density. It means that the funding calls are dispersing their support to multiple and complex research fields as the time passes, thereby increasing the network density. Which, in contrast, does not mean that all fields are increasing their strategic position (i.e., betweenness centrality) both equally and simultaneously. Furthermore, while for the 2007-2010 government, the average area priority (i.e., mean betweenness centrality index by area) was led by life science, followed by physical, social/humanities, and health sciences, for the 2011-2014 government, the leading position was taken by health sciences—the remaining areas maintained their rank. The two leading positions for the 2015-2018 government were constant for health and life sciences. However, social/humanities surpassed physical sciences for the first time. At the individual level, fields such as general medicine; public health, environmental and occupational health; and energy (renewable energy, sustainability and the environment; or general energy) were among those emphasized with higher betweenness across periods.

Figs. 7-9 display the bibliographic coupling networks reflecting the national research fronts by period. Out of the total of 334 fields covered by the ASJC, Colombia shows below-average mature research incursion with 45.5% of research fronts identified in the bibliographic network in 2011-2014, 46.4% in 2015-2018, and 46.7% in 2019-2022. In 2011-2014, of the entire sub-set of fields of social sciences/humanities, 63% were identified as part of the national research front, followed by life sciences (53%), physical sciences (51%), and health sciences (23%). In 2015-2018, 64% were of the social sciences/humanities, followed by life sciences (60%), physical sciences (51%), and health sciences (21%). In 2019-2022, 64% were also of the social sciences/humanities, followed by life sciences (60%), physical sciences (52%), and health sciences (21%). Notice that the overall

composition of research fronts by area has been essentially fixed over the last 12 years. A common factor found across periods is the higher betweenness of the multidisciplinary field and general-wider fields (e.g., general engineering; general biochemistry, genetics and molecular biology; general agricultural and biological sciences; general medicine; general chemistry). Also, the weight of the links and endogenous consistency by area seem remarkably robust within the physical sciences axis. It is crucial to highlight that the bibliographic coupling network is modeled based on references and the number of references changes according to discipline. For instance, the number of references used in articles from health and medical science is significantly higher than mathematics or computer sciences (Gingras 2014).

Figs. 10-12 present the correlations between strategic fields of funding calls and national research fronts of the subsequent period. An overall visual inspection suggests no strong correlation between strategic fields in funding calls and strategic fields in the research fronts in the subsequent period. The first general feature to notice is the mismatch between STIP and national research fronts. We determine the percentage of fields shared in an accumulated bibliographic network produced by articles published between 1996-2022 and the funding calls 2007-2018. For social sciences/humanities it was 60%, life sciences 51%, physical sciences 45%, and health sciences 21%. In sum, social sciences/humanities fields have the most similarities between STIP and research fronts, while health sciences have fewer.

Table 3 displays the results of the Pearson correlations between funding calls and research fronts betweenness centrality of fields. Out of 334 ASJC research fields, 67 showed any betweenness score in both samples in 2007-2010 STIP and 2011-2014 research calls; 69 in 2011-2014 and 2015-2018; and 97 in 2015-2018 and 2019-2022. Thus, in relative terms, the latter comparable periods increased in shared fields. However, considering the complete set of ASJC fields, the number of shared strategic fields is rather small. STIP and research fronts strategic fields were moderate (considering the reduced sub-set of fields with any betweenness centrality score). STIP 2007-2010 and research fronts 2011-2014 were found to be moderately correlated [$r(65) = .42, p < .001$]. STIP 2011-2014 and research fronts 2015-2018 also were found to be moderately correlated [$r(67) = .32, p < .01$]. STIP 2015-2018 and research fronts 2019-2022 also were found to be moderately correlated [$r(95) = .41, p < .001$]. Fields with both above-average betweenness centrality and consecutive appearances in STIP and research fronts in all periods examined included public health, environmental and occupational health; general medicine; and infectious diseases (in the case of health sciences); general agricultural and biological sciences; agronomy and crop science; and drug discovery (for life sciences); general energy; renewable energy, sustainability and the environment; and fuel technology (for physical sciences); and economics and econometrics; and sociology and political science (for social sciences and humanities).

4 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The STIP drive of each government seems to be partially disconnected from the previous administration—as expected—and considerably disconnected from the national research fronts. Colombian STIP is getting more intricate and complex—not to mention multi/trans/inter-disciplinary (Cortés & Ramírez-Cajiao 2023b, 2023a). There is an increasing role of research fields to be part of funding calls, particularly for 2019-2022. For 2007-2010 government, there were 91 out of 334 research fields with $0 >$ betweenness centrality, while for 2019-2022, that number increased to 176. The latter government 2019-2022 brought together an international ‘*Misión de Sabios*’ (MinCiencias 2019a). It is the second version. The first was done in the 90s. Such a congregation aimed to gather over 40 local/international experts to help the government design the national STIP in the long run. The broad and diverse scope of this version is noticeable by establishing eight thematic focuses: biotechnology, bioeconomy and the environment; basis and space sciences; life and health sciences;

social sciences, human development and equality; sustainable energy; creative and cultural industries; ocean and hydrobiological resources; convergent technologies, nano/info/cogno industries 4.0 (MinCiencias 2019b).

A study with a similar aim, although a different approach based on research output, also found a misalignment between the global development agenda—a policy-wise issue—and countries' research priorities. Findings showed that there is a substantial misalignment between the global production of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)-related research and SDG challenges (Confraria et al. 2024). For instance, while there is an alignment between countries' research priorities and SDG challenges only for SDG1 (No poverty), SDG2 (Zero hunger), SDG6 (Clean water and sanitation), and SDG9 (Industry, innovation, and infrastructure), for all other SDGs there was found a misalignment or an inconclusive relationship between SDG challenges and research prioritization. So, there were higher challenges for a country in a given SDG but no local research priorities were aligned to address those challenges. The authors outlined diverse plausible causes, such as inequality in research funding and capabilities, historical research specialization, socioeconomic and political factors, institutional and structural barriers, and global knowledge distribution.

The national STIP follows along a global STIP trend, where quantity is the main course for a successful academic career and also the primary indicator for national comparisons: number of publications, patents, scientists, citations, and—as shown here—the number of research fields included in STIP and funding calls (Chu & Evans 2021). This trend is also visible in the structure of scientific production and citations. Increasing coauthorship and multi-university research collaboration could explain the cross-subdiscipline interrelation growth (Jones et al. 2008; Varga 2019; Wuchty et al. 2007). Despite the growing research fields supported by funding calls, research fronts have remained fixed for over a decade. As a result, the number of fields identified was below the average of the total established by the ASJC standard, with the majority from the social sciences and humanities, followed by life sciences, physical sciences, and health sciences. That is in line with the predictive feature of science mapping techniques to identify the established scientific capabilities of countries (Börner et al. 2012; Cortés 2022; Guevara et al. 2016; Huang et al. 2021; Schiebel 2012).

A visual structure characteristic of the bibliographic coupling network unveils the robust interrelationships between physical sciences fields, which aligns with the Hierarchy of Sciences hypothesis. Disciplines such as physical sciences work toward consensus/agreement, while social sciences and humanities work toward dissension/disagreement (Cortés 2021, 2022; Fanelli & Glänzel 2013). It was also noticeable in the fields with higher betweenness centrality throughout 2011-2022, which consisted of *hard sciences* (e.g., general engineering; general biochemistry, genetics and molecular biology; general agricultural and biological sciences; general chemistry). Elements usually wielded for such a divergence between *hard* and *soft* sciences consensus vary, from the complexity of phenomena analyzed (e.g., being society more complex than cell activity) and (des)centralization of funding (i.e., more centralized in *hard* sciences), to methodological approaches (i.e., more organic and contextual in *soft* sciences) (Lamers et al. 2021).

Our results also align with higher-income countries' national STIP assessments. A study determined the relationship between national policies and university staff changes in Denmark (Stage & Aagaard 2020). Despite finding a profound effect of such policies on Danish universities, such changes seldom have been instantaneous, direct, or immediate (Stage & Aagaard 2020). Path dependency might be one of the main explanatory factors for the relatively static dynamic of national research fronts in our findings and the seldom direct relationship between Danish STIP policies and their impact on staff since it is a crucial feature that shape/modify local or global STIP (Arnold 2004; Stage & Aagaard 2020).

Path-dependence —in our study’s context— means that new elements (e.g., government vision of science) should adapt and interlock with the existing conditions of the STIP and national knowledge production system (David 1994). Elements explaining such a self-reinforcing dynamic are: i) accumulation of experience, ii) the crystallization of expectations, iii) the widening circle of their diffusion, iv) the diffusion of the knowledge thereof, v) and of the actions predicated upon that knowledge. For the case of research organizations (e.g., research groups, centers, universities), path-dependence is also related to positive returns (i.e., doing things in a particular already-known fashion, such as researching in a particular field, yields effects of doing similar things on the next stage) (Coombs & Hull 1998). Failures that might explain the gap between STIP design and implementation/impact could be the institutional bottleneck (i.e., administrative/government deficits), a common adversity for middle-low income countries such as Colombia (Acemoglu et al. 2012; Svarc et al. 2011). Such a path has received the influence of geographical, historical, and economic factors. For instance, South America has a comparative advantage in botany research over Russia due to the presence and access to highly biodiverse ecosystems such as the Amazon rainforest (Miao et al. 2022).

An additional path-dependency related factor that might constrain Colombia’s science system is that its higher education system followed — and still is, with a few exceptions — a model of a teaching-based ecosystem instead of a research-based one. Despite the foundation of a few universities by religious orders in the XVII century (Martínez 2018), the strengthening of the higher education system in the XIX century followed a Napoleonian model of professional training, in contrast with the Humboldtian model of higher education which also promoted research activities and layout the principles of the modern higher education system (Pritchard 2004; Vasen et al. 2023). The late adoption of the latter model and the path-dependency such adoption carried on, among other factors, delayed the introduction of the country into the international science arena until the 1990s (Cortés & Andrade 2022a; Fundación Alejandro Ángel Escobar 2007). Just recently, it was established the Ministry of Science Technology and Innovation in 2020 as an upgrade of Colciencias, the National Council of Science founded back in 1968 (Congreso de Colombia 2021; Fog 2013). In sum, the teaching over the research based higher education system path dependency, the late establishment of key government bodies, and the lack of recourses available to invest in the science systems adds up to the difficulty of developing new and more sophisticated research fronts.

Does all the above suggest that Colombia’s below-average diversification of research fronts will be determined and governed by its path dependence toward a lock-in scenario? Literature on *relatedness* (Hidalgo et al. 2007; Neffke et al. 2018; Neffke & Henning 2013), argues that if a low-income country wants to progress in its economic stage, it will have to change its economic structure from being more related from simple products to complex ones (Pinheiro et al. 2022). The success, however, depends on the timing of the economic structure and a diversification policy into effect (i.e., it could be costly and inefficient if a diversification policy enters into effect when there is a low/null level of economic structure diversification). Both internal (e.g., research and development, education) and external factors (e.g., high-skilled migrants, international scientific collaboration) have an essential role in such a dynamic. However, the latter discussion should be taken with caution since the core study discussed (i.e., Pinheiro et al., 2022), was based on international trade data, not bibliographic data.

Our analysis also found a moderate correlation between both STIP and research fronts, with two major caveats: there is a wide gap between the increasing fields supported by funding calls and research fronts where the most matched area is the one with the highest dissension/disagreement (i.e., social sciences and humanities); and there are even fewer fields in both STIP and research fronts with any strategic and consecutive relevance for governments transition. A first reflection is that Colombia has been implementing a diversification STIP for a non-yet-ready or interlocked national system with

stagnated research fronts. According to the *relatedness* literature (Pinheiro et al. 2022), this is the problematic scenario in which a diversification policy comes when there is a middle-low level of diversification in national research fronts. That agrees with Colombian current STIP difficulties, which have been discussed elsewhere (Cortés & Andrade 2022a, 2022b).

A finding to be explored further could be those shared fields with higher betweenness centrality for both STIP and research fronts and their relationship with economic growth. For example, a study argued that scientific areas such as engineering and technology, base clinical, pre-clinical and health, foster national economic performance (Pinto & Teixeira 2020). We found similar fields that scored above-average betweenness centrality and consecutive appearances in STIP and research fronts in all periods (e.g., public health, environmental and occupational health; general medicine; and infectious diseases; drug discovery). If those fields could be key to leapfrogging (Perez & Soete 1990) to more complex/diversified fields for the Colombian case, remains an open question.

Our study is not free of limitations. The potential feedback loop between STIP priorities, research fronts, and the internal or external influence is not examined in-depth here. For instance, the country's research fronts can guide policy-makers on building capacities for the forthcoming STIP, which can be prioritized based on the highlighted fields or the vision of policy-makers, taking into account the changing dynamics of global science. Future research could investigate how STIP, research fronts, and different factors interact and influence each other. Further inquiries could explore a more direct relationship between STIP and its effect on the national science system, for instance, funding allocation in a given field and the effect on the growth or switch of the scientific workforce specialized in such a field. The use of bibliographic databases with a broader coverage (e.g., Google Scholar, Dimensions) or different from the research fronts (e.g., development/improvement or exports of goods/services). Finally, multiple country-region-cases comparisons would shed light on the STIP and research fronts dynamic in different geographic, institutional, or scientific development stages.

REFERENCES

- Acemoglu, D., García-Jimeno, C., & Robinson, J. A. (2012). 'Finding Eldorado: Slavery and long-run development in Colombia', *Journal of Comparative Economics*, 40/4: 534–64. DOI: 10.1016/j.jce.2012.07.003
- Ahrweiler, P., Schilperoord, M., Pyka, A., & Gilbert, N. (2015). 'Modelling research policy: Ex-ante evaluation of complex policy instruments', *JASSS*, 18/4. University of Surrey. DOI: 10.18564/jasss.2927
- Aria, M., & Cuccurullo, C. (2017). 'bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis', *Journal of Informetrics*, 11/4: 959–75. Elsevier Ltd. DOI: 10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007
- Arnold, E. (2004). 'Evaluating research and innovation policy: A systems world needs systems evaluations', *Research Evaluation*, 13/1: 3–17. Oxford University Press. DOI: 10.3152/147154404781776509
- Avellar, A. P. M. D., & Botelho, M. D. R. A. (2018). 'Impact of innovation policies on small, medium and large Brazilian firms', *Applied Economics*, 50/55: 5979–95. Routledge. DOI: 10.1080/00036846.2018.1489109
- Bastian, M., Heymann, S., & Jacomy, M. (2009). 'Gephi: an open source software for exploring and manipulating networks'. *International AAAI Conference on Weblogs and Social Media*.

- Block, H.-J., & Krull, W. (1990). 'What are the consequences? Reflections on the impact of evaluations conducted by a science policy advisory body', *Scientometrics*, 19/5–6: 427–37. Kluwer Academic Publishers. DOI: 10.1007/BF02020705
- Bodmer, W. (1994). 'The influence of charitable foundations on medical Research policy', *Journal of Medical Engineering and Technology*, 18/4: 138–42. Informa Healthcare. DOI: 10.3109/03091909409030792
- Börner, K., Klavans, R., Patek, M., Zoss, A. M., Biberstine, J. R., Light, R. P., Larivière, V., et al. (2012). 'Design and update of a classification system: The ucsd map of science', (N. R. Smalheiser, Ed.) *PLoS ONE*, 7/7: e39464. Public Library of Science. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0039464
- Bornmann, L., Bowman, B. F., Bauer, J., Marx, W., Schier, H., & Palzenberger, M. (2012). 'Standards for applying bibliometrics to the evaluation of research institutes in the natural sciences [Standards für die anwendung der bibliometrie bei der evaluation von forschungsinstituten im bereich der naturwissenschaften]', *Zeitschrift für Evaluation*, 11/2: 233–60.
- Boswell, C., & Smith, K. (2017). 'Rethinking policy “impact”': Four models of research-policy relations', *Palgrave Communications*, 3/1. Palgrave Macmillan Ltd. DOI: 10.1057/s41599-017-0042-z
- Boyack, K. W., & Klavans, R. (2010). 'Co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, and direct citation: Which citation approach represents the research front most accurately?', *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61/12: 2389–404. DOI: 10.1002/asi.21419
- Bozeman, B., & Link, A. N. (2015). 'Toward an assessment of impacts from US technology and innovation policies', *Science and Public Policy*, 42/3: 369–76. Oxford University Press. DOI: 10.1093/scipol/scu058
- Bush, V. (1945). *Science, the endless frontier - A Report to the President by Vannevar Bush, Director of the Office of Scientific Research and Development*. Washington.
- Callon, M., Courtial, J. P., & Laville, F. (1991). 'Co-word analysis as a tool for describing the network of interactions between basic and technological research: The case of polymer chemistry', *Scientometrics*, 22/1: 155–205. Kluwer Academic Publishers. DOI: 10.1007/BF02019280
- Callon, M., Courtial, J.-P., Turner, W. A., & Bauin, S. (1983). 'From translations to problematic networks: An introduction to co-word analysis', *Social Science Information*, 22/2: 191–235. SAGE Publications. DOI: 10.1177/053901883022002003
- Chu, J. S. G., & Evans, J. A. (2021). 'Slowed canonical progress in large fields of science', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 118/41: e2021636118. National Academy of Sciences. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.2021636118
- Colciencias. (2005). 'Convocatorias'. *Convocatorias Colciencias*. Retrieved September 5, 2022, from <<https://legadoweb.minciencias.gov.co/convocatorias>>

- Confraria, H., Ciarli, T., & Noyons, E. (2024). 'Countries' research priorities in relation to the Sustainable Development Goals', *Research Policy*, 53/3: 104950. North-Holland. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2023.104950
- Confraria, H., Mira Godinho, M., & Wang, L. (2017). 'Determinants of citation impact: A comparative analysis of the Global South versus the Global North', *Research Policy*, 46/1: 265–79. Elsevier B.V. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2016.11.004
- Congreso de Colombia. (2021). *Ley 2162 de 2021.*, pp. 1–9. Bogotá: Congreso de Colombia.
- Constitución Política de Colombia. (1991). *Capítulo 4 del Título 7 De los ministros y directores de los departamentos administrativos. Constitución Política de Colombia.* Bogotá.
- Coombs, R., & Hull, R. (1998). 'Knowledge management practices' and path-dependency in innovation', *Research Policy*, 27/3: 237–53. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(98\)00036-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(98)00036-5)
- Cortés, J. D. (2021). 'Dissension or consensus? Management and business research in Latin America and the Caribbean'. Glänzel W., Heeffer S., Chi P.-S., & Rousseau R. (eds) *18th International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics, ISSI 2021*, pp. 293–8. Leuven, Belgium: International Society for Scientometrics and Informetrics.
- . (2022). 'Identifying the dissension in management and business research in Latin America and the Caribbean via co-word analysis', *Scientometrics*, 127/12: 7111–25. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-021-04259-5
- Cortés, J. D., & Andrade, D. A. (2022a). 'The Colombian scientific elite—Science mapping and a comparison with Nobel Prize laureates using a composite citation indicator', *Plos One*, 17/5: e0269116. Bogotá, Colombia: Public Library of Science. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0269116
- Cortés, J. D., & Andrade, D. A. (2022b). 'Winners and runners-up alike?—a comparison between awardees and special mention recipients of the most reputable science award in Colombia via a composite citation indicator', *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9/1: 217. DOI: 10.1057/s41599-022-01241-1
- Cortés, J. D., Guix, M., & Carbonell, K. B. (2021). 'Innovation for sustainability in the Global South: bibliometric findings from management & business and STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) fields in developing countries', *Heliyon*, 7/8: e07809. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07809
- Cortés, J. D., & Ramírez-Cajiao, M. C. (2023a). 'The Policy is Dead, Long Live the Policy — Science Technology and Innovation Policy Research Priorities and Government Transitions via Multilayer Network Analysis', *In preparation*.
- . (2023b). 'The Content Structure of Science Technology and Innovation Policy — Applying co-word analysis to funding calls in Colombia'. Sserwanga I., Goulding A., Moulaison-Sandy H., Du J. T., Soares A. L., Hessami V., & Frank R. D. (eds) *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*2, pp. 187–96. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

- Crouch, D., Irvine, J., & Martin, B. R. (1986). 'Bibliometric analysis for science policy: An evaluation of the United Kingdom's research performance in ocean currents and protein crystallography', *Scientometrics*, 9/5–6: 239–67. Kluwer Academic Publishers. DOI: 10.1007/BF02017247
- David, P. A. (1994). 'Why are institutions the "carriers of history"?: Path dependence and the evolution of conventions, organizations and institutions', *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 5/2: 205–20. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0954-349X\(94\)90002-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0954-349X(94)90002-7)
- Davis, S. W. (1989). 'The Impact of Funding on the Formulation of Research Policy', *Accountability in Research*, 1/1: 33–45. DOI: 10.1080/08989628908573772
- DNP, 2021. (2021). 'Búsqueda bibliográfica'. Retrieved September 1, 2022, from <<https://www.dnp.gov.co/atencion-al-ciudadano/Paginas/busqueda.aspx>>
- Edler, J., Berger, M., Dinges, M., & Gök, A. (2012). 'The practice of evaluation in innovation policy in Europe', *Research Evaluation*, 21/3: 167–82. DOI: 10.1093/reseval/rvs014
- Engle, S., & Whalen, S. (2012). 'Visualizing distributed memory computations with hive plots'. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, pp. 56–63. DOI: 10.1145/2379690.2379698
- Fanelli, D., & Glänzel, W. (2013). 'Bibliometric Evidence for a Hierarchy of the Sciences', *PLOS ONE*, 8/6: e66938. Public Library of Science.
- Fog, L. (2013). 'Historia social e institucional de Colciencias'. Salazar M. (ed.) *Colciencias cuarenta años: entre la legitimidad, la normatividad y la práctica*, pp. 23–4. OCyT - Universidad Nacional de Colombia - Universidad del Rosario: Bogota.
- Fortin, J.-M., & Currie, D. J. (2013). 'Big Science vs. Little Science: How Scientific Impact Scales with Funding', *PLOS ONE*, 8/6: 1–9. Public Library of Science. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0065263
- Freeman, L. C. (1977). 'A Set of Measures of Centrality Based on Betweenness', *Sociometry*, 40/1: 35–41. [American Sociological Association, Sage Publications, Inc.]. DOI: 10.2307/3033543
- Fundación Alejandro Ángel Escobar. (2007). *Fundación Alejandro Ángel Escobar - 50 Años*. (C. Forero, Ed.). Bogotá: Fundación Alejandro Ángel Escobar.
- Gates, A. J., Ke, Q., Varol, O., & Barabási, A. L. (2019). 'Nature's reach: narrow work has broad impact', *Nature*, 575/7781: 32–4. Nature Publishing Group. DOI: 10.1038/d41586-019-03308-7
- Gingras, Y. (2014). *Bibliometrics and research evaluation - Uses and abuses*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press.
- Gök, A., & Edler, J. (2012). 'The use of behavioural additionality evaluation in innovation policy making', *Research Evaluation*, 21/4: 306–18. DOI: 10.1093/reseval/rvs015
- Gök, A., Rigby, J., & Shapira, P. (2016). 'The impact of research funding on scientific outputs: Evidence from six smaller European countries', *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67/3: 715–30. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23406>

- Gonzalez-Brambila, C. N., Reyes-Gonzalez, L., Veloso, F., & Perez-Angón, M. A. (2016). 'The scientific impact of developing nations', *PLoS ONE*, 11/3: 1–14. Public Library of Science. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0151328
- De Gorter, H., & Swinnen, J. F. M. (1998). 'Impact of economic development on commodity and public research policies in agriculture', *Review of Development Economics*, 2/1: 41–60. Blackwell Publishing Ltd. DOI: 10.1111/1467-9361.00027
- Guevara, M. R., Hartmann, D., Aristarán, M., Mendoza, M., & Hidalgo, C. A. (2016). 'The research space: using career paths to predict the evolution of the research output of individuals, institutions, and nations', *Scientometrics*, 109/3: 1695–709. Springer Netherlands. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-016-2125-9
- Guskov, A., Kosyakov, D., & Selivanova, I. (2016). 'Scientometric research in Russia: impact of science policy changes', *Scientometrics*, 107/1: 287–303. Springer Netherlands. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-016-1876-7
- Hicks, D., & Isett, K. R. (2020). 'Powerful numbers: Exemplary quantitative studies of science that had policy impact', *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1/3: 969–82. MIT Press. DOI: 10.1162/QSS_A_00060
- Hidalgo, C. A., Winger, B., Barabási, A. L., & Hausmann, R. (2007). 'The product space conditions the development of nations', *Science*, 317/5837: 482–7. American Association for the Advancement of Science . DOI: 10.1126/science.1144581
- Himanen, L., Auranen, O., Puuska, H.-M., & Nieminen, M. (2009). 'Influence of research funding and science policy on university research performance: A comparison of five countries', *Science and Public Policy*, 36/6: 419–30. DOI: 10.3152/030234209X461006
- Huang, Y., Glänzel, W., & Zhang, L. (2021). 'Tracing the development of mapping knowledge domains', *Scientometrics*, 126/7: 6201–24. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-020-03821-x
- Inglesi-Lotz, R., & Pouris, A. (2011). 'Scientometric impact assessment of a research policy instrument: The case of rating researchers on scientific outputs in South Africa', *Scientometrics*, 88/3: 747–60. Kluwer Academic Publishers. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-011-0440-8
- Ioannidis, J. P. A., Klavans, R., & Boyack, K. W. (2016). 'Multiple Citation Indicators and Their Composite across Scientific Disciplines', *PLoS Biology*, 14/7: 1–17. Public Library of Science. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pbio.1002501
- Isaksen, A., Normann, R. H., & Spilling, O. R. (2017). 'Do general innovation policy tools fit all? Analysis of the regional impact of the Norwegian Skattefunn scheme', *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 6/1. SpringerOpen. DOI: 10.1186/s13731-017-0068-x
- Ito, A., Li, Z., & Wang, M. (2017). 'Multi-level and Multi-route Innovation Policies in China: A Programme Evaluation Based on Firm-level Data', *Millennial Asia*, 8/1: 78–107. SAGE Publications Ltd. DOI: 10.1177/0976399616686866
- Jasinski, A. H. (2003). 'Has innovation policy an influence on innovation? The case of a country in transition', *Science and Public Policy*, 30/6: 431–40. Beech Tree Publishing. DOI: 10.3152/147154303781780245

- Jones, B. F., Wuchty, S., & Uzzi, B. (2008). 'Multi-university research teams: Shifting impact, geography, and stratification in science', *Science*, 322/5905: 1259–62. DOI: 10.1126/science.1158357
- Jordan, G. B. (2010). 'A theory-based logic model for innovation policy and evaluation', *Research Evaluation*, 19/4: 263–73. DOI: 10.3152/095820210X12827366906445
- Katz, J. S. (2000). 'Scale-independent indicators and research evaluation', *Science and Public Policy*, 27/1: 23–36. Oxford Academic. DOI: 10.3152/147154300781782156
- Kessler, M. M. (1963). 'Bibliographic coupling between scientific papers', *American Documentation*, 14/1: 10–25. Wiley. DOI: 10.1002/asi.5090140103
- Krzywinski, M., Birol, I., Jones, S. J., & Marra, M. A. (2012). 'Hive plots-rational approach to visualizing networks', *Briefings in Bioinformatics*, 13/5: 627–44. DOI: 10.1093/bib/bbr069
- Kuhlmann, S. (2003). 'Evaluation of research and innovation policies: A discussion of trends with examples from Germany', *International Journal of Technology Management*, 26/2–4: 131–49. Inderscience Publishers. DOI: 10.1504/ijtm.2003.003366
- Lamers, W. S., Boyack, K., Larivière, V., Sugimoto, C. R., VANECK, N. J., Waltman, L., & Murray, D. (2021). 'Investigating disagreement in the scientific literature', *eLife*, 10. eLife Sciences Publications Ltd. DOI: 10.7554/eLife.72737
- Li, Y., Mao, J., Zhang, L., Wang, D., Shen, S., & Huang, Y. (2022). 'How scientific research incorporates policy: an examination using the case of China's science and technology evaluation system', *Scientometrics*. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-021-04215-3
- Louder, E., Wyborn, C., Cvitanovic, C., & Bednarek, A. T. (2021). 'A synthesis of the frameworks available to guide evaluations of research impact at the interface of environmental science, policy and practice', *Environmental Science and Policy*, 116: 258–65. Elsevier Ltd. DOI: 10.1016/j.envsci.2020.12.006
- Magro, E., & Wilson, J. R. (2013). 'Complex innovation policy systems: Towards an evaluation mix', *Research Policy*, 42/9: 1647–56. Elsevier B.V. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2013.06.005
- . (2019). 'Policy-mix evaluation: Governance challenges from new place-based innovation policies', *Research Policy*, 48/10. Elsevier B.V. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2018.06.010
- Mansfield, E. (1991). 'Academic research and industrial innovation', *Research Policy*, 20/1: 1–12. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-7333\(91\)90080-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0048-7333(91)90080-A)
- . (1998). 'Academic research and industrial innovation: An update of empirical findings|This paper was based on work supported by grants from the National Science Foundation. A preliminary version was presented at the annual meetings of the American Economic Association', *Research Policy*, 26/7: 773–6. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(97\)00043-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(97)00043-7)
- Martínez, J. S. A. (Ed.). (2018). *Un largo camino. Universidad del Rosario, 365 años*. Bogotá: Editorial Universidad del Rosario.

- McNie, E. C., Parris, A., & Sarewitz, D. (2016). 'Improving the public value of science: A typology to inform discussion, design and implementation of research', *Research Policy*, 45/4: 884–95. North-Holland. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2016.01.004
- Meyer-Krahmer, F. (1984). 'Evaluation of Industrial Innovation Policy—Concepts, Methods and Lessons', *Review of Policy Research*, 3/3–4: 467–75. DOI: 10.1111/j.1541-1338.1984.tb00142.x
- Miao, L., Murray, D., Jung, W. S., Larivière, V., Sugimoto, C. R., & Ahn, Y. Y. (2022). 'The latent structure of global scientific development', *Nature Human Behaviour*, 6/9: 1206–17. DOI: 10.1038/s41562-022-01367-x
- MinCiencias. (2019a). 'Misión de Sabios'. Retrieved September 16, 2022, from <https://minciencias.gov.co/mision_sabios>
- . (2019b). 'Focos temáticos | Misión de Sabios'. *Focos temáticos | Misión de Sabios*. Retrieved January 25, 2023, from <https://www.minciencias.gov.co/mision_sabios/focos>
- . (2022a). 'Plan de convocatorias ASCTeI 2023-2024 | Minciencias'. Retrieved July 19, 2023, from <<https://minciencias.gov.co/plan-convocatorias-asctei-2023-2024>>
- . (2022b). 'Convocatorias Minciencias'. *Convocatorias Minciencias*. Retrieved November 1, 2022, from <<https://www.minciencias.gov.co/convocatorias/todas>>
- Nakamura, M., Pendlebury, D., Schnell, J., & Szomszor, M. (2019). *Navigating the Structure of Research on Sustainable Development Goals*. Philadelphia, US: Institute for Scientific Information.
- Neal, H., Smith, T., & McCormick, J. (2008). *Beyond Sputnik - U.S. Science Policy in the Twenty-First Century*. *Beyond Sputnik*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press. DOI: 10.3998/MPUB.22958
- Neffke, F., Hartog, M., Boschma, R., & Henning, M. (2018). 'Agents of Structural Change: The Role of Firms and Entrepreneurs in Regional Diversification', *Economic Geography*, 94/1: 23–48. Routledge. DOI: 10.1080/00130095.2017.1391691
- Neffke, F., & Henning, M. (2013). 'Skill relatedness and firm diversification', *Strategic Management Journal*, 34/3: 297–316. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. DOI: 10.1002/smj.2014
- Nielsen, K. (2003). 'Social capital and the evaluation of innovation policies', *International Journal of Technology Management*, 26/2–4: 205–25. Inderscience Publishers. DOI: 10.1504/ijtm.2003.003370
- Nikzad, R. (2019). 'Evaluation of Canadian innovation policy: locating innovation policy among other policies', *International Journal of Business Continuity and Risk Management*, 9/1: 70–96. Inderscience Publishers. DOI: 10.1504/IJBCRM.2019.096699
- Opsahl, T., Agneessens, F., & Skvoretz, J. (2010). 'Node centrality in weighted networks: Generalizing degree and shortest paths', *Social Networks*, 32/3: 245–51. North-Holland. DOI: 10.1016/j.socnet.2010.03.006

- Pahl, D., Wilson, W., Evans, R., Kowalski, L., Vickery, J., & Costa, D. (2008). 'Research, policy, and evaluation: Systematic interaction informs air quality decisions', *Research Evaluation*, 17/4: 251–63. DOI: 10.3152/095820208X378288
- Perez, C., & Soete, L. (1990). 'Catching up in technology: entry barriers and windows of opportunity'. *Technical change and economic theory*, pp. 458–79.
- Pianta, M., & Sirilli, G. (1997). 'Impact of innovation policies: Evidence from the Italian innovation survey', *Science and Public Policy*, 24/4: 245–53. Beech Tree Publishing. DOI: 10.1093/spp/24.4.245
- Pinheiro, F. L., Hartmann, D., Boschma, R., & Hidalgo, C. A. (2022). 'The time and frequency of unrelated diversification', *Research Policy*, 51/8: 104323. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2021.104323
- Pinto, T., & Teixeira, A. A. C. (2020). 'The impact of research output on economic growth by fields of science: a dynamic panel data analysis, 1980–2016', *Scientometrics*, 123/2: 945–78. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-020-03419-3
- Pohoryles, R. J. (2006). 'Innocult revisited: The impact of EU research programmes on national research policies, key actors and research collaboration', *Innovation*, 19/1: 107–16. Routledge. DOI: 10.1080/13511610600607999
- Pritchard, R. (2004). 'Humboldtian values in a changing world: Staff and students in German universities', *Oxford Review of Education*, 30/4: 509–28. Taylor & Francis Ltd . DOI: 10.1080/0305498042000303982
- Rigby, J. (2011). 'Systematic grant and funding body acknowledgement data for publications: New dimensions and new controversies for research policy and evaluation', *Research Evaluation*, 20/5: 365–75. DOI: 10.3152/095820211X13164389670392
- Rigby, John. (2011). 'Systematic grant and funding body acknowledgement data for publications: New dimensions and new controversies for research policy and evaluation', *Research Evaluation*, 20/5: 365–75. DOI: 10.3152/095820211X13164389670392
- Rodríguez-Navarro, A., & Brito, R. (2022). 'The link between countries' economic and scientific wealth has a complex dependence on technological activity and research policy', *Scientometrics*, 127/5: 2871–96. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-022-04313-w
- Russo, M., & Rossi, F. (2009). 'Cooperation networks and innovation: A complex systems perspective to the analysis and evaluation of a regional innovation policy programme', *Evaluation*, 15/1: 75–99. DOI: 10.1177/1356389008097872
- Samara, E., Georgiadis, P., & Bakouros, I. (2012). 'The impact of innovation policies on the performance of national innovation systems: A system dynamics analysis', *Technovation*, 32/11: 624–38. DOI: 10.1016/j.technovation.2012.06.002
- Schiebel, E. (2012). 'Visualization of research fronts and knowledge bases by three-dimensional areal densities of bibliographically coupled publications and co-citations', *Scientometrics*, 91/2: 557–66. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-012-0626-8

- Scopus. (2020). 'What is the complete list of Scopus Subject Areas and All Science Journal Classification Codes (ASJC)?'. Retrieved December 10, 2021, from <https://service.elsevier.com/app/answers/detail/a_id/15181/supporthub/scopus/>
- . (2022). 'Scopus - Document search'. Retrieved June 1, 2020, from <<https://bit.ly/3KhKoDn>>
- Shibayama, S., & Baba, Y. (2015). 'Impact-oriented science policies and scientific publication practices: The case of life sciences in Japan', *Research Policy*, 44/4: 936–50. Elsevier B.V. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2015.01.012
- Shiffrin, R. M., & Börner, K. (2004). 'Mapping knowledge domains', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 101/SUPPL. 1: 5183–5. National Academy of Sciences. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0307852100
- Shugars, S., & Scarpino, S. V. (2021). 'One outstanding path from A to B', *Nature Physics*, 17/4: 540. DOI: 10.1038/s41567-021-01222-2
- Singh, V. K., Singh, P., Karmakar, M., Leta, J., & Mayr, P. (2021). 'The journal coverage of Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions: A comparative analysis', *Scientometrics*, 126/6: 5113–42. Springer Science and Business Media B.V. DOI: 10.1007/S11192-021-03948-5/FIGURES/5
- Stage, A. K., & Aagaard, K. (2020). 'National policies as drivers of organizational change in universities: A string of reinforcing reforms', *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1/2: 849–71. DOI: 10.1162/qss_a_00046
- Statista. (2020). 'How Long Can World Leaders Serve?'. *Chart: How Long Can World Leaders Serve?* Retrieved January 26, 2023, from <<https://www.statista.com/chart/18074/term-limits-of-selected-heads-of-government/>>
- Svarc, J., Laznjak, J., & Perkovic, J. (2011). 'Unintended consequences of innovation policy programmes: Social evaluation of the technological projects programme in Croatia', *Innovation: Management, Policy and Practice*, 13/1: 77–94. eContent Management Pty Ltd. DOI: 10.5172/impp.2011.13.1.77
- The World Bank. (2022). 'DataBank'. *DataBank*. Retrieved October 18, 2022, from <<https://databank.worldbank.org/home.aspx>>
- Thelwall, M., & Sud, P. (2022). 'Scopus 1900–2020: Growth in articles, abstracts, countries, fields, and journals', *Quantitative Science Studies*, 3/1: 37–50. DOI: 10.1162/qss_a_00177
- Torregrosa-Hetland, S., Pelkonen, A., Oksanen, J., & Kander, A. (2019). 'The prevalence of publicly stimulated innovations –A comparison of Finland and Sweden, 1970–2013', *Research Policy*, 48/6: 1373–84. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2019.02.001
- UNESCO. (2010). *National science, technology and innovation systems in Latin America and the Caribbean*. (G. A. Lemarchand, Ed.). Montevideo: UNESCO Office Montevideo.
- Varga, A. (2019). 'Shorter distances between papers over time are due to more cross-field references and increased citation rate to higher-impact papers', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 116/44: 22094–9. National Academy of Sciences. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1905819116

- Vasen, F., Sarthou, N. F., Romano, S. A., Gutiérrez, B. D., & Pintos, M. (2023). 'Turning academics into researchers: The development of National Researcher Categorization Systems in Latin America', *Research Evaluation*. DOI: 10.1093/RESEVAL/RVAD021
- Waltman, L., & Larivière, V. (2020). 'Special issue on bibliographic data sources', *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1/1: 360–2. MIT Press - Journals. DOI: 10.1162/qss_e_00026
- Wang, J. (2013). 'Citation time window choice for research impact evaluation', *Scientometrics*, 94/3: 851–72. DOI: 10.1007/s11192-012-0775-9
- Wang, N., Liang, H., Jia, Y., Ge, S., Xue, Y., & Wang, Z. (2016). 'Cloud computing research in the IS discipline: A citation/co-citation analysis', *Decision Support Systems*, 86: 35–47. School of Economics and Management, Jiangsu University of Science and Technology, China: Elsevier B.V. DOI: 10.1016/j.dss.2016.03.006
- Weber, K. M., Kubezko, K., Kaufmann, A., & Grunewald, B. (2009). 'Trade-offs between policy impacts of future-oriented analysis: Experiences from the innovation policy foresight and strategy process of the City of Vienna', *Technology Analysis and Strategic Management*, 21/8: 953–69. DOI: 10.1080/09537320903262314
- Wuchty, S., Jones, B. F., & Uzzi, B. (2007). 'The Increasing Dominance of Teams in Production of Knowledge', *Science*, 316/5827: 1036–9. American Association for the Advancement of Science. DOI: 10.1126/science.1136099
- Zhang, D., Banker, R. D., Li, X., & Liu, W. (2011). 'Performance impact of research policy at the Chinese Academy of Sciences', *Research Policy*, 40/6: 875–85. DOI: 10.1016/j.respol.2011.03.010

FIGURES

Para el logro de este objetivo se plantean cuatro acciones concretas: En primer lugar, la implementación de un programa de análisis y estudio permanente de **áreas estratégicas** según capacidades científicas y tecnológicas y dotaciones naturales con un **mecanismo de revisión periódico** para establecer cambios en caso de ser necesarios. Las áreas estratégicas son no excluyentes y deben responder a problemas presentes, pero el énfasis está puesto en que la focalización de recursos y acciones permita aprovechar oportunidades futuras de desarrollo. Como punto de partida, se han identificado las siguientes áreas estratégicas: **energía y recursos naturales; biotecnología; salud; materiales y electrónica; tecnologías de información y comunicaciones²⁴, logística y diseño, y por último, construcción de ciudadanía e inclusión social.**

Figure 1 Example of policy text section with key areas/research fields. Source: DNP (2021).

Fig. 2 Bibliographic coupling. Source: Kessler (1963)

Fig. 3 Bibliographic coupling adjusted by journal field. Source: Kessler (1963)

Fig. 4 Co-word analysis of funding research calls. Source: Callon et al. (1983)

Fig. 5 Methodology summary

Fig. 6 Betweenness indices of research fields by area and period of the funding calls, 2007-2018. Source: the authors based on Cortés and Ramírez-Cajiao (2023a). Note: only top-ten betweenness fields by period were labeled

Fig. 7 Bibliographic coupling network 2011-2014. Source: the authors based on Scopus (2022) and processed using Gephi (Bastian et al. 2009). Note: the size of the nodes is proportional to their betweenness index. The color of the nodes was based on a frequency ranking of the research field: the more orange it gets, the highest the frequency of the research field in the journals where the article was published—a field-production proxy. The color of the links was based on a frequency ranking of the edge between fields: the purple it gets, the highest the frequency of the edges between fields—the weight of the link between two fields. Only the top-five betweenness index fields by area were labeled. Consider this notation for Figs. 8 and 9.

Fig. 8 Bibliographic coupling network 2015-2018. Source: the authors based on Scopus (2022) and processed using Gephi (Bastian et al. 2009).

Fig. 9 Bibliographic coupling network 2019-2022. Source: the authors based on Scopus (2022) and processed using Gephi (Bastian et al. 2009).

Fig. 10 Correlation between research fields betweenness of funding calls, 2007-2010 and bibliographic coupling, 2011-2014. Source: the authors based on Cortés and Ramírez-Cajiao (2023a) and Scopus (2022). Note: only top/bottom-four betweenness centrality for funding calls fields were labeled

Fig. 11 Correlation between research fields betweenness of funding calls, 2011-2014 and bibliographic coupling, 2015-2018. Source: the authors based on Cortés and Ramírez-Cajiao (2023a) and Scopus (2022). Note: only top/bottom-four betweenness centrality for funding calls fields were labeled

Fig. 12 Correlation between research fields betweenness of funding calls, 2015-2018 and bibliographic coupling, 2019-2022. Source: the authors based on Cortés and Ramírez-Cajiao (2023a) and Scopus (2022). Note: only top/bottom-four betweenness centrality for funding calls fields were labeled

TABLES

Table 1 Bibliometric descriptives of the Colombian scientific production in research articles indexed in Scopus 1996-2022

Subject area	# articles
Medicine	32.202
Agricultural and biological sciences	21.185
Engineering	16.439
Social sciences	15.588
Physics and astronomy	12.766
Affiliation	
Universidad Nacional de Colombia	16.058
Universidad de Antioquia	14.721
Universidad de Los Andes	10.066
Universidad del Valle	7.461
Pontificia Universidad Javeriana	6.226
Journal	
Dyna	1.352
Biomedica	1.084
Espacios	1.034
Plos One	918
Revista Colombiana de Cardiología	894

Source: Scopus (2022).

Table 2 Full and normalized research field counts from paired journals via bibliographic coupling for the top-ten research fields by subject area.

Subject area and research fields	Full counts	Normalized counting by field 0-10
Health Sciences		
Infectious Diseases	41319	2,4
Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health	32804	1,9
General Medicine	18693	1,1
Microbiology (medical)	13005	0,8
Pharmacology (medical)	11467	0,7
General Veterinary	11224	0,7
Cardiology and Cardiovascular Medicine	7948	0,5
Veterinary (miscellaneous)	5215	0,3
Psychiatry and Mental Health	3827	0,2
Obstetrics and Gynecology	3298	0,2
Life Sciences		
General Agricultural and Biological Sciences	72152	1,5
Food Science	48114	1,0
Animal Science and Zoology	44746	0,9
Ecology, Evolution, Behavior and Systematics	41980	0,9
General Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology	35010	0,7
Aquatic Science	26055	0,6
Parasitology	19857	0,4
Biochemistry	19509	0,4
Drug Discovery	19233	0,4
Molecular Medicine	17171	0,4
Physical Sciences		
Nuclear and High Energy Physics	782835	2,5
Physics and Astronomy (miscellaneous)	400870	1,3
Engineering (miscellaneous)	280408	0,9
General Physics and Astronomy	153630	0,5
General Chemistry	85252	0,3
General Materials Science	83977	0,3
General Chemical Engineering	62007	0,2
Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment	60850	0,2
Instrumentation	59390	0,2

Condensed Matter Physics	57555	0,2
Social Sciences & Humanities		
Strategy and Management	63036	1,3
Geography, Planning and Development	51342	1,1
General Business, Management and Accounting	44698	1,0
Business and International Management	37823	0,8
Management of Technology and Innovation	33753	0,7
Management Science and Operations Research	26337	0,6
Sociology and Political Science	21986	0,5
Marketing	13743	0,3
Economics and Econometrics	13471	0,3
General Social Sciences	12770	0,3

Source: Scopus (2022).

Table 3 Pearson correlations between funding calls and research fronts betweenness centrality of fields

Periods analyzed	Fields with betweenness score in funding calls and research fronts	Correlation	p-value	95% confidence interval
Research fields betweenness of funding calls, 2007-2010 and bibliographic coupling, 2011-2014	67	0.42	0.00033	0.20; 0.60
Research fields betweenness of funding calls, 2011-2014 and bibliographic coupling, 2015-2018	69	0.32	0.006498	0.09; 0.52
Research fields betweenness of funding calls, 2015-2018 and bibliographic coupling, 2019-2022	97	0.41	2.308e-05	0.23; 0.56

Source: the authors based on Cortés and Ramírez-Cajiao (2023a) and Scopus (2022).

